

INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' THINKING

Tojiboev M.N.

Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Senior teacher of the Department of Psychology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14562400>

Key words: technology, thinking, structure, attitude, phenomenon, principle, thinking, lesson.

Annotation: In the article, depending on what area of the objective world a person knows, his thinking reflects the specific characteristics of the dialectic of development of things and events in it, the importance of the culture of thinking in the acquisition and formation of certain characteristics, as well as innovative approaches to the development of pedagogical thinking of students.

When it comes to the use of innovative education in the current period of development of science and society, it is appropriate to talk about the new research conducted in this direction in the last decade, which theoretically enriches and expands the scope of the practical application of this approach.

The goal of education is achieved when there is a clear algorithm of the teacher's actions, methods, methods, and educational tools, with the help of which the educational result should be obtained. It is important to implement a comprehensive approach to education in order to achieve the goals. Its meaning is the application of knowledge, skills and abilities available in the field of pedagogy. They must be interconnected and form a certain mechanism attached to an object.

Human thinking is the product and ability of his brain, to reflect and perceive real reality with the help of mental operations, to penetrate into the essence of the development laws of nature, society and intellectual activity. This is the basis of a person's attitude to the world, knowledge, assimilation, and change of reality. Depending on which area of the objective world a person knows, his thinking reflects the specific characteristics of the dialectic of the development of things and events in it, acquires certain characteristics, becomes an important type and is formed.

The development of pedagogical thinking of students is related to the development of their own experience recorded in reflection, it is to find the foundations of ready-made methods of educational activity of students and pedagogical influence on their personality, to strictly formalize the foundations of new methods and to implement them in a technological form. representation is also related to making certain pedagogical decisions at a certain time and anticipating events.

Thinking is included in various parts of pedagogical activity, so its content becomes student's action and perception. Diversity of pedagogical thinking requires certain skills and culture from the teacher.

Pedagogical thinking culture is manifested in the teacher's thinking about his thinking processes, thinking critically and designing formalized thinking. The culture of thinking is carried out through the professional way of thinking of an expert, which is a stereotypical

structure that changes very slowly and with great difficulty. This occurs due to the manifestation of obstacles in the system of "education-education" relations in the teacher's work (Yu. V. Senko). These obstacles appear as a rejection of the humanization of education and the principles of modern pedagogical thinking: understanding, dialogicity, reflexivity, metaphor implementation.

Such barriers may include:

- tendency of the teacher to specific definitions of pedagogical phenomena, which have a strong attitude towards the pedagogue;
- on the basis of determining the meaningful aspects of the concepts of "learning" and "teaching", combining the image of students and their real educational opportunities.

These are:

- lack of connection between the principles of presence and developmental education in the teacher's practical activity and the methodological component of the educational material;
- lack of requirements for the normative-value content of his professional activity in the professional model of the future specialist created by the teacher;
- leads to one-sidedness and fragmentation of the teacher's activity, which sometimes does not allow him to understand the need for the joint activity of the entire pedagogical team;
- leads the teacher to understand various concepts as a set of technologies.

For the teacher, didactic laws force him to implement methodological recommendations without entering into the logic of justification.

Method. In the real conditions of pedagogical activity, four motives for the emergence of thinking have been identified, which affect creativity to a certain extent (O.M. Krasnoryadseva).

1. Reflection occurs in order to determine the causes of the events and, if problems, failures or difficulties arise, to return the teaching activity to the intended direction. The teacher tries to return to what is reflected in the lesson plan, to restore the planned course of the lesson.

2. The motive may be the teacher's desire to get out of pedagogical monotony. Getting out of monotony is based on the teacher's perception of the "professional image of the world", the characteristics of the educational material or the level of preparation of students.

3. The teacher's moral and professional values become a motive for creative thinking. In this case, these values play the role of an opportunity for professional self-development of the teacher and his students.

4. Motive - the need to accept a task that is not formed by the teacher himself, but which requires the teacher to perform it. For example, pedagogical councils or science departments may have tasks assigned to the pedagogical team.

When talking about the maturity of thinking, it is necessary to determine the specific characteristics of scientific thinking, which is an important indicator of the teacher's culture and competence:

- systemic thinking - the ability to acquire a wide range of knowledge for multi-dimensional illumination of phenomena, to identify the complexes of their interrelated components in subsystems, to solve problems;
- determinism of thinking - the ability to establish cause-and-effect relationships, to understand the connection between events in the pedagogical system;

- the ability to think - the ability to identify and predict possible ways of developing the educational process, actions of individuals, groups and communities;
- concreteness of thinking - the ability to transfer (use) the general rules of the theory to explain current facts and situations, analyze them and draw quick conclusions;
- perspective thinking - the ability to see the perspective of events, to model the "near development zone";
- economic thinking - the ability to choose the path that requires the least effort and time, the shortest methods of solving problems;
- reflexivity of thinking - the ability to evaluate one's activity from the outside, as if through the eyes of students;
- heuristic thinking - the ability to form and test hypotheses, filter alternatives based on various criteria, create information, draw conclusions (L.F. Spirin).

Results and discussion. Based on the description of the important features of pedagogical thinking, it should be noted that it helps to understand professional pedagogical activity, allows to raise it to the level of creativity, prevents and eliminates atypical pedagogical situations, and also stimulates pedagogical activity.

It is appropriate to use pedagogical technologies in the application of innovative approaches to the development of pedagogical thinking of students. In order to understand the nature of the contradictions of modern innovations in education, first of all, it is necessary to determine the nature of the social motives that motivated the reform of educational institutions in our time. The first of the motives is the inconsistency between the pace of development of the school and the pace of development of society. By the end of the 20th century, this gap had increased dramatically as a result of the industrial and information revolutions. In other words, at the beginning of the 21st century, it is impossible to prepare schoolchildren for life with the techniques and ideas of the 20th century. He does not play his formative role in society. In some cases, it prepares students not for life, but for exams.

The field of education The second, less strong social motive of the reforms in Together with the social and scientific-technical revolutions, human society entered the period of "rapid" development. The competition of social systems and the information revolution created the necessary conditions for the rapid operation of the economic mechanism.

Thus, a society of "fast" development creates a need for a "new" education system capable of responding to the "new" people, the acceleration of the development of all spheres of social life. Innovative processes in the educational system more or less consciously respond to these social demands.

The very concept of "innovation" appeared for the first time in the 19th century in the scientific research of cultural scientists and meant the introduction of some elements of one culture into another. Pedagogical innovation processes from the end of the 50s with the emergence of the traditions of reforming the educational system, Western scientists S. Frene and R. Galya, group work method R. Cousin (France); person-oriented education, "Talent Search" program (USA), Waldorf schools, M. Montessori's "Children's House" and others became the object of special research.

Innovative processes in education were widely developed in the 60s and 80s. The mass movement related to the search for new reforms, means and content of school education expanded the ideas about the methods of managing the intellectual and moral development of schoolchildren. The emergence of authorship curriculums, which express the high

professional culture and spiritual aspirations of creators, has become an important complication of breaking the traditional system that determines the content of education at school. Programs developed by artists and musicians: (B.M. Nemensky, D.D. Kabalevsky), philosophers (V.S. Bibler, G.S. Batishev), writers and mathematicians (E.N. Ilin, P.M. Erdniev, etc.) was a channel for the penetration of new ideas such as revision. Innovations covered not only educational activities, but also children's extracurricular time. Various organizational forms of the joint life of children and adults combined with cultural and production projects (restoration, charity, ecology, historical-educational tourism, interpersonal communication) have been determined. Innovative forms of actions aimed at humanizing closed children's institutions - orphanages, boarding schools for children with disabilities - began to work. The separatist attitude towards the upbringing of children with various forms of emotional and mental disabilities began to break down, and new experiences for the successful development of such children mixed with the environment of normal children appeared.

The practice of reforms faced a serious contradiction between the existing need for the development of innovative processes and the readiness of teachers to implement them. First of all, according to our point of view, the concepts of "new", "innovation", "innovation", "innovative process", and "innovative activity" should be used freely.

Within the innovative approach to the development of students' pedagogical thinking, the individual's right to individual creative contribution, personal initiative, and freedom of self-development is realized.

It can be seen that there are different models of innovative education in modern psychology and pedagogy, but the main feature of the innovative strategy in the educational process is personality development. The basis of such models is the principle of joint creative activity of teachers and students, which is implemented according to two conditions of development: a) student's activity; b) his cooperation with the teacher. Education is carried out by solving creative problems related to increasing readiness for the future, forming expectations.

So, innovations are fundamentally new forms of activity that allow to achieve a high level of quality.

An innovative approach to the development of students' pedagogical thinking, if there is a comprehensive theoretical and technological concept of renewal, will be the basis for the development of a creative, healthy, highly educated person.

The transition from traditional education to innovative education leads to the democratization of the relationship of teachers and teachers with students, to abandoning the strict union of the social roles of "teacher - student" in educational conditions, to the development of cooperation (from authoritarian management - the transition to cooperative activities; from reproductive educational tasks to productive and creative mental activities) increases the problem of readiness to accept new social positions. Even if the creative ability and professional skills of the teacher are high, it is a difficult task to master the methods of changing personal attitude, democratizing relations and communication with students.

Conclusion. Creative thinking, cooperation, culture of communication and culture of activity, self-awareness and the need for student's self-awareness, professional competence - this is the basis of a teacher's professional activity in an innovative school.

All this is an innovative education in which the tasks of the educational process in the innovative transformation of education are solved comprehensively based on the principles of

mutual enrichment, mutual respect, cooperation of teachers, students, parents, and the administration. indicates that a lim field should be created. Also, consider and distinguish specific content of education that introduces children to the practice of personal self-management (managing their feelings, intuition, communication, behavior and ways of projecting their "I"). showing is important.

In addition, the innovative approach to the development of pedagogical thinking of students is another aspect that provides a clear understanding of the development of advanced technologies, the reform of goals and strategies, the analysis and evaluation of introduced innovations, and the creation of conditions for their development and application - management culture and democratization should be emphasized.

The main directions of the innovative approach to the development of pedagogical thinking of students:

- development of the educational field of the school;
- scientific and methodical works;
- continuity and consistency of education (1st and 2nd stages of education);
- linguistics, modular education;
- university stages, "talented children" and specialized schools;
- integration;
- corrective and developmental education;
- environmental education and training;
- school television;
- military-patriotic education;
- development of abilities and talents;
- health of students and teachers;
- psychological-pedagogical diagnosis;
- Joint management and self-management of educational work through the educational program "I am a person", "I am a person".

The effectiveness of the predicted pedagogical conditions that ensure the development of the educational sector was controlled according to the following criteria:

- child's health (complex medical diagnosis);
- level of physical development;
- mental state of the child;
- learning motivation;
- level of education;
- dynamics of personality development;
- participation in creative laboratories and groups;
- activity and self-assessment;
- educational efficiency;
- carrying out scientific expertise of educational programs and teachers' activities;
- the quality of the teacher's scientific and innovative work.

The comparative analysis of the data shows the dynamics of mastering effectiveness, integrated, accelerated, modular, person-oriented, developmental physical and mental education impact on health status, the emotional state of the level of intellectual development based on classification, the role of the school interior, the style of communication in adapting

schoolchildren to new educational conditions, the effect of combining classes based on the effectiveness of health-treatment and preventive measures, etc. allowed to determine.

In the context of new problems of education: humanization, stratification, individualization, integration, the need to create an educational model that has the main importance in the personality and development of students has become urgent. Comprehensive analysis of the creative capabilities of the teaching team, directions for updating the educational content: creating a developmental education system that assumes the integrity of knowledge, in-depth study of subjects, establishing interdisciplinary relations, integration, modular education, made it possible to define a holistic picture of the worldview through early specialist classes.

References:

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Buyuk kelajagimizni mard va oliyanob xalqimiz bilan birga quramiz. – T.: O'zbekiston, 2017. – 488 b.
2. Normadovich, Tojiboyev Marat. "A model for designing individual educational trajectories of students-future teachers of school organizations." *Horizon: Journal of Humanity and Artificial Intelligence* 2.5 (2023): 548-554.
3. Тожибоев Марат Нормадович. "Талабаларнинг педагогик тафаккурини ривожлантиришга инновацион ёндашув" *Science and innovation*, vol. 2, no. Special Issue 10, 2023, pp. 147-153. doi:10.5281/zenodo.10035426.
4. Djuraev R.X. Ta'limda interfaol texnologiyalar. Sano-standart, – T., 2010.- 87 b.
5. Ibragimov X., Abdullaeva Sh. Pedagogika. O'quv qo'llanma. – T., Fan, 2004. -182 b.
6. Кабалевский Д.Б. Сила искусства. - М.: Мол. гвардия, 1984. - 142 с.
7. Турсунов А 2022 ЧАҚИРУВГА ҚАДАР БОШЛАНГИЧ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИК МАШҒУЛОТЛАРИДА ПЕДАГОГИК ВА ИННОВАЦИОН ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИ ҚЎЛЛАШ ВА УЛАРНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ТОМОНЛАРИ *Science and innovation*, 1(В3), 432- 434
8. Abdurasulov, J. (2024). PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF MILITARY PATRIOTIC EDUCATION IN GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS. В *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY* (Т. 4, Выпуск 7, сс. 38–40). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12721051>
9. Тожибоев Марат Нормадович ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК ТАФАККУРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШГА ИННОВАЦИОН ЁНДАШУВ // SAI. 2023. №Special Issue 10. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/talabalarning-pedagogik-tafakkurini-rivozhlantirishgainnovatsion-yondashuv>
10. Abdurasulov J. (2024). HARBIY PEDAGOGIKANING BOSHQA FANLAR BILAN ALOQASI. Молодые ученые, 2(6), 48–52. извлечено от <https://inacademy.uz/index.php/yo/article/view/28164>